

COMPARISON OF PICTURE FRAME DEVICES AND ANALYSIS OF LOCKING ANGLE FOR FABRICS WITH DIFFERENT CROSS-PLY ANGLES

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents a comparative characterisation of the shearing behaviour of different textiles. In the first part (Section 2), standard picture frame (PF) tests using two classic PF devices as well as a modified, novel kind of shear testing device are discussed. The different devices are compared by testing a commingled glass fibre/polypropylene (PP) woven fabric similar to the one used by Cao et al. [1].

In the second part of this paper (Section 3), the standard cruciform 0°/90° woven samples are replaced: carbon fibre non-crimp fabric (NCF) materials are investigated, gradually reducing the relative fibre angles of the textiles from ±45° to ±22.5°. Such a reduction is of special interest for the manufacturing of stiffening elements in the aircraft industry. In this context, 0° reinforcement layers tend to induce draping related issues and their substitution by reinforcements with smaller cross-ply angles could provide a solution.

1 INTRODUCTION

One of the de-facto standard methods for the investigation of fabric locking angles during shearing is the picture frame test [2]. A cruciform woven textile sample is mounted in the PF device and its two fibre directions are aligned with the frame arms. The device is mounted in a testing machine and a tensile load is applied to two opposite corners. Ideally, the fabric is subjected to pure trellis shear.

One advantage of the PF test is the simple evaluation of the shear angle γ . Values for γ can directly be related to the displacement d of the testing machine, the initial cross-ply angle θ_0 and the picture frame hinge distance L_{frame} (see Equations 1 and 2). The relation between shear angle and shear force is specific for each textile and the characteristic locking angle marks the onset of draping defects such as wrinkling [3]. Before testing, it is important to precisely prepare and mount the sample in the PF device as misalignments and unbalanced clamping can cause significant deviations in test results [4].

$$\cos \theta = \cos \theta_0 + \frac{d}{2L_{frame}} \quad (1)$$

$$\gamma = 2 \cdot (\theta_0 - \theta) \quad (2)$$

For the manufacturing of stiffening elements, most layups currently contain 0° layers which are oriented along the longitudinal stiffener axis. These unidirectional layers provide the required strength and stiffness in the final part but in contrast have poor deformation characteristics. Almost instantaneous wrinkling upon shear deformation during preforming is a common issue and the numerous manual sub

steps are time-consuming and costly.

Previous studies discovered that a layup of $\pm 45^\circ$ fabric with 0° support layers can be replaced by a $\pm 30^\circ$ fabric [5]. In doing so, the shearability of the material is enhanced by eliminating the 0° plies. At the same time, strength and stiffness along the longitudinal stiffener axis are enhanced by rotating the plies of the biaxial fabric towards the 0° direction. Automating manufacturing processes with such $\pm\theta_0$ fabrics promise a large potential in terms of production rate increase and cost reduction.

It is however expected that the usable range regarding fabric shear deformation decreases with shallower cross-ply angles. A detailed investigation of the difference in locking angle behaviour is therefore necessary in order to establish and validate the applicability of $\pm\theta_0$ fabrics.

2 COMPARATIVE PICTURE FRAME CHARACTERISATIONS

In this section, three different picture frame apparatus are compared: one picture frame at Swinburne University which is vertically mounted on a Zwick Z010 testing machine, one picture frame at the University of Stuttgart which is horizontally mounted on a test rig and a novel kind of shear testing rig (ST) also situated at the University of Stuttgart (both designed in-house). In accordance with [1], the crucial geometrical parameters L_{frame} and L_{fabric} can be seen in Figure 1. Their actual values for the different apparatus are summarised in Table 1 and are used for normalising the recorded shear force according to the commonly applied energy method [6].

Figure 1: Geometric parameters of PF test apparatus.

Frame parameter	PF Stuttgart	PF Swinburne	ST Stuttgart
L_{frame}	145 mm	220 mm	306 mm
L_{fabric}	100 mm	140 mm	174 mm
Clamping method	Metal bar and screw-in bolts	Metal bar and screw-through bolts	Segmented clamps, pneumatically actuated

Table 1: PF parameters.

2.1 Description of different picture frame test setups

The two picture frame apparatus are shown in Figure 2. They share a similar general design: both frames include bearings in the hinges and the fabric can be clamped via a metal plate which is attached to the frame by three bolts on each frame arm. However, the Swinburne University PF uses a screw-through connection whereas the University of Stuttgart PF possesses screw-in bolts. This results in slightly different clamping boundary conditions: The textile of the Stuttgart PF is attached up to the middle of the metal plate whereas the yarns cover the entire width of the metal plate in the Swinburne PF.

Figure 2a: PF Stuttgart.

Figure 2b: PF Swinburne.

For the fixation of the test samples in both apparatus, the frames are locked into position by an auxiliary device (cf. Figure 2b) to ensure the correct frame angle. A board is placed in the middle of the frame and the fabric is laid on the flat surface. The Swinburne sample preparation uses an additional transparent grid in order to have an enhanced control of the fibre orientations. The Stuttgart PF is equipped with markings in the clamping area which help controlling fibre orientations. One after the other, the metal plates are attached to the four sides of the frame and the torque of the screws is confined to a low, constant value. Opposite sides are attached consecutively and the textile is manually flattened while mounting the screws. The limitation of the clamping forces is of special interest as it can lead to in-plane tension. Elevated in-plane tension is known to have an influence on the resulting force vs. shear angle curves of the PF test [7].

2.2 Description of the shear testing rig

The shear testing rig is designed to create complex textile deformations and is based on a picture frame design [8], see Figure 3. The different degrees of freedom are highlighted by arrows: the rig incorporates segmented boundary conditions (light blue) and each side can be moved laterally while measuring emerging in-plane forces (yellow). The classical PF deformation (dark blue) can be performed thanks to pillar bearing mountings as well as the attachment to a spindle drive.

Figure 3: Shear testing rig Stuttgart.

As illustrated, each side of a textile can be manipulated by 7 independently moving clamps. The segmented clamps are 3D printed and equipped with springs. As they are designed to move independently from each other, there is a small gap (~1 mm) between each of them. The clamps are opened and closed collectively using levers which are actuated by pneumatic cylinders. In addition to the classical picture frame deformation, the four clamping zones can move in a range of 200 mm, enabling tests such as the bias-extension or bias-bias-extension. The mechanisms enabling these movements are equipped with tensile force sensors which allow the measurement of the forces induced by segmented as well as collective displacements.

Arming the shearing test rig with textile samples for the picture frame test requires a board which is placed in the middle of the frame on the exact level of the opened clamps. While manually holding the textile sample in place, the individual yarns are inserted in the clamps using a metal sheet. Once this is performed on all four sides, the clamping mechanisms are activated simultaneously on all four sides. Due to this arming procedure as well as the size of the test rig, sagging can occur depending on the textile architecture.

2.3 Benchmarking exercise vs. Cao et al. 2008

Material and test procedure

For validation purposes of the present shear test setups, experiments using a material similar to the one used by Cao et al. [1] are performed. It was however not possible to obtain the exact same material as the manufacturer does not exist anymore. Characteristic properties of the present textile (which can be seen in Figure 2a) are compared to the textile of the benchmark study by Cao et al. in Table 2.

<i>Fabric parameter</i>	<i>Cao et al (2008)</i>	<i>This study</i>
<i>Fibre type</i>	Commingled glass fibre/PP 60/40	
<i>Architecture</i>	Balanced 2x2 Twill weave	
<i>Areal weight</i>	1485 gsm	785 ± 19 gsm
<i>Yarn width w</i>		
<i>Warp</i>	1.62 mm	4.55 ± 0.27 mm
<i>Weft</i>	2.32 mm	5.04 ± 0.21 mm
<i>Ends or Picks/cm n</i>		
<i>Warp</i>	5.56	2.03 ± 0.02
<i>Weft</i>	3.75	1.97 ± 0.01

Table 2: Benchmarking fabric parameters.

As shown, the glass/PP weave used in this study has roughly half the areal weight and thicker yarns in both warp and weft directions. As a consequence, a deviation of the shear force levels can be expected.

With each of the three shear test set-ups the glass/PP weave is tested up to a shear angle of 60°. Each sample is sheared multiple times and at least 6 valid experiments are evaluated. Every test consists of two consecutive shearing operations and both deformations are analysed in this study. This is due to the expectation that the second deformation has a lower scatter which makes comparison easier, cf. [9].

Analysis and data handling

The test results are analysed with a MATLAB algorithm and the routine is briefly explained hereafter. The measured dataset (time, displacement, crosshead force) of each individual test is extracted from the testing machine files. In a first step, the crosshead displacement of the testing machine is converted into the corresponding shear angles as demonstrated in Equations 1 and 2. Furthermore, the tensile load data from the testing machine is converted into the related shear load and normalised according to the energy method, cf. Equations 3 and 4 [6].

As this study involves fabrics other than $\pm 45^\circ$ (see Section 3), the initial shear area of the sample is not necessarily a square and a factor of $\sin(2\theta_0)$ is included in the normalisation equation. Subsequently, the shear force data is interpolated to an evenly spaced grid of shear angle values (0.5° steps). The force contribution of the empty frame is deducted from the test values in order to obtain pure textile shear data. From these results, the average values, minimum & maximum values, standard deviation and coefficient of variance are calculated for the experiments.

$$F_{shear} = \frac{F - F_{frame}}{2 \cos \theta} \quad (3)$$

$$F_{shear, norm} = F_{shear} \cdot \frac{L_{frame}}{L_{fabric}^2 \cdot \sin 2\theta_0} \quad (4)$$

Finally, the locking angle is obtained by a linearisation of the average value curve of each experiment series. This linearisation is also executed via a MATLAB code using different numbers of linearisation base points, ranging from four to seven. For each linear approximation, the end of the section with the shallowest slope is where the material starts locking, cf. [10]. The median locking angle of all four linearisations is saved at the end which can then be utilised for comparisons between test set-ups or fabrics.

Results and Conclusions

In Figure 4, the results of the benchmark tests are plotted according to the above-mentioned procedure showing the normalised results of both of the PF apparatus as well as the ST. Both the first and the second repetitions are shown in Figure 4a, respectively Figure 4b. In addition to the average value curves, standard deviations as well as the calculated locking angles are illustrated.

Figure 4a: Test results glass fibre/PP weave on all three set-ups, 1st run.

Figure 4b: Test results glass fibre/PP weave on all three set-ups, 2nd run.

It can be observed that the qualitative results of all three devices compare well with each other for both of the repetitions and that the locking angles lie closely together. As expected, deviations and scatter are lower for the second repetition of the shearing.

However, it is clear that the level of shear force is considerably lower for the tests performed with the shear testing rig (pink curves and y-axes). This can be explained by the previously mentioned clamping procedure which leads to a noticeably higher sagging compared to both of the PF apparatus. As a consequence, in-plane tension is lower which has previously been linked to lower shear force levels by other researchers [11].

Finally, the shear force levels of the PF devices can be compared to the results of the benchmark exercise by Cao et al. and they qualitatively express the same behaviour. As anticipated however, the results differ from each other in terms of the shear force level as different textiles were employed. A ratio between the shear force levels of approximately 5 can be estimated.

The energy method uses geometric characteristics of different PF devices for the normalisation of the test results. If this method is to be extended for a comparison of different textiles, inherent fabric parameters need to be taken into account. A purely geometric approach requires information on the crossover friction areas as well as the number of side-by-side friction contacts per unit cell as they correlate with the actual level of friction during shearing.

Figure 5a: Unit cell yarn crossover area in terms of yarn width and thread count. Figure 5b: Side-by-side friction contacts in a fabric unit cell.

Figure 5a outlines how the crossover area in a unit cell correlates to the yarn widths w and thread counts n . The multiplication of the four geometric parameters (two per yarn direction) provides a relative factor of yarn area versus unit cell area. The larger this factor, the larger is the crossover area which is proportionally impacting the magnitude of the shear force level. Figure 5b shows the side-by-side contacts between individual yarns which are represented by the dashed lines. The higher the thread counts n in a unit cell, the higher the number of friction interfaces. Similarly to the crossover area, friction force levels are estimated to be proportionally affected by the number of side-by-side contacts. In accordance with the geometric findings from Figure 5, Equation 4 can be extended as follows:

$$F_{Shear,norm,mod} = F_{Shear} \cdot \frac{L_{frame}}{L_{fabric}^2 \cdot \sin 2\theta_0} \cdot \frac{1}{w_{warp} \cdot n_{warp} \cdot w_{weft} \cdot n_{weft}} \cdot \frac{1}{n_{warp} \cdot n_{weft}} \quad (5)$$

The first newly added term describes the crossover area whereas the following term relates to the number of side-by-side friction contacts which is directly linked to the thread counts. The normalisation with these additional terms results in a correction factor of 4.43 (Equation 6), which is close to the initially estimated difference in shear force levels between the results of the benchmark of Cao et. al. and this study. Values for yarn widths and thread counts are taken from Table 1.

$$CF = \frac{(w_{warp} \cdot n_{warp}^2 \cdot w_{weft} \cdot n_{weft}^2)_{Cao}}{(w_{warp} \cdot n_{warp}^2 \cdot w_{weft} \cdot n_{weft}^2)_{This\ study}} = 4.43 \quad (6)$$

By including geometrical factors in the normalisation, an increased correlation between both studies is provided and the comparability of results is suggested. However, the authors would like to emphasise that this additional normalisation factor is purely geometric and a discussion on the applicability of this theory is necessary. Further investigations are required.

3 ANALYSIS OF LOCKING ANGLE FOR FABRICS WITH DIFFERENT CROSS-PLY ANGLES

The second part of this study focuses on the comparison of locking angles of non-crimp fabrics with different cross-ply angles. After having established a consistent shear behaviour of the test set-ups in the first part of this paper, samples of different NCFs with varying cross-ply angles are tested on each set-up. It has been demonstrated in literature that the shear behaviour of a given fabric depends on its parameters such as weave type, stitching type or stitching tension [12]. It is therefore crucial to compare three fabrics that only vary in fibre orientation.

3.1 Shear/elongation theory for curved stiffeners

Curved stiffening elements feature different bending radii across the profile cross-section. The ratio between the longest and shortest arc length can be described as the elongation ε . When preforming the curved stiffener shape from a biaxial material with cross-ply angle θ_0 , the required shear angle γ is geometrically dependent from both the elongation and the cross-ply angle [13]. The principle can be illustrated with the picture frame drawings in Figure 1.

Let the side length of a unit cell be dominated as L_{frame} , while the unit cell diagonal and the cross-ply angle in the undeformed state are titled θ_0 and L_f , respectively (Equation 7). During the shear deformation, the unit cell diagonal increases proportionally to the elongation factor ε , the cross-ply angle decreases to θ , while L_{frame} remains constant (Equation 8). By substituting Equations 7 and 8, the new fibre orientation can be derived as shown in Equation 9.

$$L_f = 2L_{frame} \cdot \cos \theta_0 \quad (7)$$

$$L_f \cdot (1 + \varepsilon) = 2L_{frame} \cdot \cos \theta \quad (8)$$

$$\theta = \cos^{-1}[(1 + \varepsilon) \cdot \cos \theta_0] \quad (9)$$

The required shear angle γ can subsequently be calculated as the difference in cross-ply angles before and after the shearing of the fabric, see Equation 10.

$$\gamma = 2 \cdot (\theta_0 - \theta) \quad (10)$$

A three-dimensional visualisation of the theoretically required shear angle as a function of elongation and cross-ply angle is depicted in Figure 6. Larger shear angles are required for greater elongations and lower initial cross-ply angles. The dashed black line traces the theoretical maximum of shear deformation for a given combination of ε and θ_0 , cf. Equations 9 and 10. Data points on this curve replicate a scenario where the fabric is sheared from its initial biaxial state with a cross-ply angle θ_0 to a unidirectional orientation of 0° . While theoretically valid, such scenarios are not applicable for actual preforming processes.

Figure 6: Required shear angle for combinations of elongation and cross-ply angle.

3.2 Testing results

The experiments for the analysis of the fabric locking angle evolution are conducted with three different NCFs. The fabric architecture is kept consistent with the fibre orientation being the only varying parameter. Details of the fabric parameters can be found in Table 3.

<i>Fabric parameter</i>	<i>BX45</i>	<i>BX30</i>	<i>BX225</i>
Fibre type	12K HS carbon fibre		
Architecture	Biaxial non-crimp fabric with PES chain stitch		
Areal weight	153 gsm (as per data sheet)		
Fibre orientation (θ_0)	$\pm 45^\circ$	$\pm 30^\circ$	$\pm 22.5^\circ$

Table 3: NCF fabric parameters.

As previously explained, three test set-ups and three fabric types are used for this experiment series. As was the case with the benchmarking experiments in the first part of this study, force vs. displacement curves are recorded not only for the first test run, but also for the second run which follows directly afterwards. In total, 18 data sets of force vs. shear angle are recorded. The evaluation of the tests with NCF samples is executed with the same MATLAB program that was outlined previously.

Figure 6 shows the normalised shear force vs. shear angle curves for the first run of all three fabrics on the picture frame at the University of Stuttgart. The typical shear force load curve can be observed, with a steep initial increase until around 2.5° of shear. Subsequently, the graph flattens and becomes more linear. All three fabrics exhibit a similar slope which confirms their identical architecture. The black squares in Figure 7 represent the locking angles that are obtained from the individual linearisations with four, five, six and seven base points. The fabric locking angle (triangle for $\pm 45^\circ$, diamond for $\pm 30^\circ$ and star for $\pm 22.5^\circ$) is the median of the four values.

Figure 7: Test results PF Stuttgart with BX45, BX30 and BX225 samples.

Tests of the BX225 fabric (green) experience a large increase in normalised shear force around the 10° mark. BX30 samples (red) lock noticeably later at around 22° and BX45 (blue) tests only exhibit locking behaviour at 44° of shear. A clear trend of decreasing locking angles for smaller cross-ply angles is visible. It can further be observed that the increase in normalised shear force after the locking angle is more severe for shallower cross-ply angles. Towards the end of the test, the fibres become increasingly aligned with the testing direction. As a result, tensile loads can potentially contribute to the overall measured force of the testing machine.

Figure 8 shows the results for the $\pm 30^\circ$ fabric that were recorded during the second run on all three test fixtures. Good correlation between the measurements of the individual fixtures is apparent. The

mathematical calculation of the locking angle does produce values that slightly vary. However, all three median locking angles are within a tolerance of 3°. The close correlation between the experiment data can be attributed to the nature of the second test run. Literature has previously shown that the results of second or third runs from the same sample are more repeatable compared to the curves of the first run.

Previously noticed influences of different clamping boundary conditions are not apparent in these results. This can be explained by the high stiffness and smaller areal weight of the NCFs which reduces sagging due to the clamping procedure to a minimum.

Figure 8: Test results BX30 samples on two PF and ST.

The median locking angles for tests with the three NCFs on different test rigs can finally be compared based on the initial fabric cross-ply angle θ_0 . Figure 9 shows the evolution of locking angle for a) the first and b) the second run of the experiments. A clear trend of decreasing locking angles for smaller cross-ply fibre orientation is obvious for both test runs. Results for the second run exhibit a closer correlation as is expected from previous studies [9].

Figure 9a: Evaluation of locking angle over cross-ply angle, 1st run.

Figure 9b: Evaluation of locking angle over cross-ply angle, 2nd run.

3.3 Forming envelope

Main goal of this study was to examine the locking behaviour of fabrics with different fibre orientations. If suitable, such materials could replace standard layups with 0° layers which possess inferior shearability. Section 3.1 outlined how the required shear angle γ for given stiffener geometries can be assessed depending on the elongation ϵ of the stiffener and the cross-ply angle of the fabric θ_0 . This data essentially constitutes the lower bound of the forming envelope for curved stiffening elements.

The results from the shear testing experiments illustrate the upper bound of the forming envelope. Shear deformations above the locking angle from the study are not feasible due to defect development

such as wrinkling. In theory, fabric material can be safely preformed with combinations of ε and θ_0 if the resulting shear angles lie between the two surfaces. An example is shown in Figure 10 with the results from the PF tests at the University of Stuttgart. The blue, red and green lines depict the locking angles which were measured at $\pm 45^\circ$, $\pm 30^\circ$ and $\pm 22.5^\circ$, respectively. The solid black line shows the intersection of both surfaces where the required shear angle and the locking angle are equal. The coloured portion of the graph outlines the envelope where preforming is feasible according to the shear elongation theory and the PF experiment results. Preforming combinations of ε and θ_0 in the grey area must be avoided as the required shear angles exceed the fabric locking angles.

Figure 10: Comparison of required shear angles and fabric locking angles.

4 CONCLUSIONS

The first part of this study confirms the consistency of the testing results amongst three different shear test rigs, namely two PFs and a novel shear test rig. Besides, an approach to compare the picture frame characterisation results of different textiles is presented which suggests a comparability of this study to the benchmark exercise by Cao et. al. [1]. This theory will need to be discussed and elaborated by the scientific community if it shall be extended to a tool for future comparative exercises.

In addition, it is confirmed that a difference in clamping conditions can potentially alter the shear behaviour, depending on the architecture of the fabric. There is a large variety of modifications to the PF tests such as clamps with rubber pads to avoid fibre slip or needle bars to avoid fibre bending. A change in boundary conditions will also influence the exact fabric locking angles while the general trend is expected to uphold.

Furthermore, this study examined the locking behaviour of three different NCFs with the three different test setups. A clear reduction of fabric locking angles with more acute cross-ply angles is evident in Figures 7, 9a and 9b. The initial hypothesis of decreasing fabric locking angles with shallower θ_0 was therefore proven.

It should be noted that the results of this study are specific to the NCF type described in Table 3. Results of shear tests are highly dependent on fabric architecture and the comparability between different types of fabrics is therefore not automatically given. While the decreasing trend should prevail, exact values of locking angles will vary with fabric type.

5 FUTURE OUTLOOK

For this study, three NCFs with different cross-ply angles of $\pm 45^\circ$, $\pm 30^\circ$ and $\pm 22.5^\circ$ were used to examine the evolution of the fabric locking angle. Data between these specific cross-ply angles was interpolated to generate the plots in Figures 9a, 9b and 10. Further research on additional fibre orientations (e.g. $\pm 40^\circ$, $\pm 35^\circ$ or $\pm 25^\circ$) will help to enhance the reliability of the locking angle trend.

During the experiment series, the dependence of fabric locking angles from the boundary conditions, mainly the clamping situation, became apparent. Preforming processes in actual manufacturing environments might not employ such strict boundary conditions, therefore the fabric locking angles

might differ from the picture frame tests. As a result, preforming trials are required to validate the shear behaviour. The preforming trials can either be conducted with a reference geometry such as the double dome or with parts from real production processes. The comparison of these preforming experiments with draping simulations can provide additional insight on the occurrence of preforming defects.

A difference in fabric tension proved to be a crucial factor during the experiments on the novel shear test rig with the benchmarking glass fibre/PP material. Since all frame clamps are closed simultaneously, there is no opportunity to “flatten” the sample as is possible with the PFs. The benchmarking fabric was roughly five times heavier than the NCFs and the weave was quite loose. As a result, the benchmark samples tended to sag before the experiment commenced. Other researchers have previously demonstrated a connection between in-plane tensions in a fabric and shear force during the test, which explains the difference in normalised shear force. The setup of the novel shear rig does however allow the controlled application of membrane tensions. This capability can be used in the future to determine the extent of the fabric tension’s influence on its shear behaviour.

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